

Diversifying Forest Production

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Mushroom and honey production in forest lands of Galicia (NW Spain).

Forest is type of land use with a strong potential to deliver ecosystems services in farming systems. The forest economic return is long, being from 8-15 years in fast-growing tree species such as *Eucalyptus* or *Poplar*, 30-45 years in species like *Pinus radiata* or *Birch* and 80-120 years in most of the EU autochthonous species. This long term return makes forest management negligible due to the investments to be done from planting, fertilizing, pruning and uncommercial thinning. This long-term economic return can be counteracted by diversifying forest production through the obtention of marketable and unmarketable products. Diversifying forest production makes forest farms more resilient to market and climate change conditions. Moreover, increasing the economic product from forest lands should contribute to revitalize the rural areas, and provide more opportunities to young foresters, able to use new techniques to produce agricultural products linked to modern value chains. Agricultural products delivery from forest lands is considered as forest farming practices within the agroforestry definition. Main marketable products are biomass for heating purposes, mushrooms, honey, small fruits like berries and livestock, besides the timber and the carbon sequestration of the trees. Moreover, unmarketable products like soil carbon sequestration, ecotourism, water quality or biodiversity also contributes to deliver ecosystem services to the society that even not sold, have a value associated to the better quality of life and health.

The economic return of the marketable and unmarketable products from forestry is still unknown but it is well-recognized as can be seen in the value chains described by the 11 value chains described in AF4EU web page.

References:
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